

Computing infrastructure for the definition, performance testing and implementation of safe-by-design approaches in nanotechnology supply chains

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To ensure crosstalk and interaction with the SbD4Nano project, in Task T1.2 we aim to develop a public repository of available information in order to link available open databases and state of art modeling approaches, as well as other relevant resources for SbD approaches application with the e-infrastructure. This deliverable describes the efforts undertaken in this task, starting with a description of the Semantic Bioactivity Landscape (Section 2), which contains an RDF version of the overview of the available resources that can be useful for a Safe-by-Design that was created for Deliverable D1.1 (Section 3). It continues with an explanation of Atena, a website which acts as a document repository service (Section 4) and an extensive description of the exposure triples in TNO's DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point. The NanoSafety Data Interface is described in Section 6, which provides user-friendly access to the aggregated search index of the (sub)set of eNanoMapper database instances. Section 7 discusses how the information described in the previous sections is integrated into the e-infrastructure. As the SbD4Nano project continues, we aim to keep developing the public repository of available databases, nano-informatics tools, and models for hazard prediction, occupational, consumer and environmental risks estimation tools, decision making tools for risk governance, and SbD strategies (Section 8).

LIST OF ACRONYMS

- API application programming interface
- CC Creative Commons (organization known for the open licenses)
- CCZero Creative Commons Zero license
- CSV comma-separated values
- df dataframe
- DSS decision support system
- DTL Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences
- ENM engineered nanomaterial
- EU European Union
- FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (an open standard)
- FDP FAIR Data Point
- HTML HyperText Markup Language
- JSON JavaScript Object Notation
- n3 Notation3
- NEP nano-enabled products
- OWL Web Ontology Language
- QSAR quantitative structure-activity relationship
- RDF Resource Description Framework (an open standard)

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- REST Representational State Transfer (an open standard)
- SbD safe-by-design
- ShEx Shape Expressions (an open standard)
- SPARQL query language for RDF
- URL Universal Resource Locator
- VoID Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets
- WP5 Work Package 5
- WWW World Wide Web
- YAML Yet Another Markup Language (an open standard)

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1. Scope and goal of the deliverable

The goal of this deliverable is to reflect the work performed under Task T1.2 on “Linking and integration with existing databases and modeling resources”. In order to link available open databases and state of art modeling approaches, as well as other relevant resources for SbD approaches application with the e-infrastructure, this task has aimed to develop a public repository of available databases, nano-informatics tools, and models for hazard prediction, occupational, consumer and environmental risks estimation tools, decision making tools for risk governance, and SbD strategies to ensure crosstalk and interaction with the project.

Figure 1: Theoretical framework for Web based repository.

One of the main objectives of the SbD4Nano project is the creation of a new e-infrastructure to promote the dialogue and collaboration between nanotechnology supply chain actors for a knowledge-based definition of safe-and-sustainable-by-design approaches regarding hazard, exposure, product performance and cost criteria. These safe-and-sustainable-by-design criteria will be developed as a decision support system (DSS) tool for the generation of a score to rank the different approaches. Therefore, the development of a web-based repository was needed within the framework of Task T1.2, to avoid collecting all existing resources in one single tool.

The main goals of this repository are the introduction of suitable workflows that allow simplified access to current databases on engineered nanomaterials (ENMs)/nano-enabled product (NEP) properties. On the other hand, the repository enables the incorporation of available modeling resources for hazard and exposure assessment, as well as electronic data formats (data schemas and templates) for automated

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data quality control analysis and (pre)processing to ensure compatibility, use and applicability of new data in existing databases and modeling resources developed by the international nano-safety community. Because of the lack of openly licensed and FAIR data, populating this repository is non-trivial. For example, while the data.search.enanomapper.net platform makes data available for many NanoSafety Cluster projects, many do not have an open license. Table 1 shows an overview of the results of an analysis of the license information of resources identified of interest (based on results in Section 2).

Table 1: Overview of the use licenses used by resources of interest. Most resources do not provide clear license information or details on how to get a license, breaking a key FAIR principle. Data from 2022-03-15.

license	count
(no license info provided)	885
unknown (http://example.com/unknown)	198
proprietary or custom (https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q50423863)	23
CCZero (http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/)	16
CC-BY (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)	6
CC-NC-SA (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/)	2
CC-NC (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/)	1
various open (https://search.data.enanomapper.net/about/enanomapper/)	1

The efforts done for the Deliverable D1.1 “Report on current gaps and limitations of existing databases, modeling approaches and knowledge to allow the implementation of SbD approaches” have served for the selection of existing resources that would be implemented in the different modules of the e-infrastructure. Only the most robust, reliable, and/or regulatory accepted will be implemented. Also, resources with an easy implementation (for example with a developed API) have been prioritized.

Figure 2: Workflow of Web Based Repository.

This deliverable explains the methodology starting from the final steps of Deliverable D1.1, i.e. converting the Excel sheet from D1.1 into the Resource Description Framework (RDF) up till the final integration of RDF into the SbD4Nano e-infrastructure. Several intermediate steps are needed, such as the development of a Semantic Bioactivity Landscape which develops a knowledge graph to indicate what database, dataset, predictive model, or general causal pattern can give some information about the bioactivity of nanomaterials; the development of a new tool to easily query information of nanocompounds published in scientific papers (implemented in *atena.urv.cat*); and the creation a repository of triplets that indicate causal relations between exposure-related factors (TNO's DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point).

The results obtained in Task T1.2 and presented in this deliverable represent the achievement of the Milestone M1.1: *“Web based repository of data, models and SbD strategies released and available”*. In addition, all work performed here will be implemented in the design and development of the e-infrastructure and the implementation of a user-friendly interface in WP5.

At the end of this project, in month 48, a new Deliverable D1.4 will be delivered aimed at updating the web-based repository with the new databases, modeling resources or SbD strategies which have been developed during the project, for instance, datasets generated in Task T3.2.

2. Semantic Bioactivity Landscape

2.1 Introduction

The purpose of the Semantic Bioactivity Landscape is to develop a knowledge graph that will tell us what database, dataset, predictive model, or general causal pattern can tell us something about the bioactivity of some nanomaterial. For this, we need not only annotate each of the knowledge sources with the

bioactivity they can tell us something about, but also which nanomaterials. This requires annotation of these sources with ontology terms and specific material identifiers. That is, we need a *knowledge graph*¹.

The content of this knowledge graph will come from many different sources, often with different licenses that we need to integrate in a single representation, so that we can integrate all sources as if they were one. Here, semantic web technologies are used, particularly the Resource Description Framework (RDF), shape expressions (ShEx), and the SPARQL query language.

2.1.1 What is on the horizon?

The information about the databases, datasets, predictive models, or general causal patterns each help us evaluate the potential risk. Databases and datasets will contain data about specific nanomaterials that we can use in a read across approach. These may also serve as training data to create predictive models, the second type of tool for a safe-by-design assessment. The models could, for example, use machine learning approaches (nanoQSAR) to predict a particular endpoint based on the structural information of the nanomaterial. Different types of predictive models exist, for example differing in taking physicochemical and/or even biological properties as input to base a prediction on. A third kind of predictive model will not directly predict an activity, but will tell us about causal relationships, which further help us think about the potential risk aspects.

Figure 3: Landscape technologies.

2.1.2 Where do these evaluation tools come from?

Table 2 provides an overview of information sources and information of the license of the metadata.

Table 2: Overview of information sources that provide metadata about various resources (databases, datasets, and models).

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge_graph

	Source	Metadata License
Databases	Manual lists	
	DIAMONDS Model FAIRpoint	proprietary
	FAIRSharing	
	WP1 collection (see Section 3)	
Datasets	Wikidata	CCZero
	NanoCommons	CCZero
	eNanoMapper	various
	WP1 collection	proprietary
Models	MODA templates	various
	eNanoMapper template (new)	
	DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point	proprietary
	AOP-Wiki	CCZero

2.2 Method

2.2.1 SbD4Nano vocabularies

A simple OWL ontology has been created for the controlled vocabulary used in the SbD landscape.

Landscape vocabulary

- URL: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/use-case-vocabulary/blob/main/landscape.owl (private repository²) This ontology contains, for example, terms like the application domains “Release/exposure assessment”, “Hazard assessment”, etc.

Gracious vocabulary

- URL: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd4nano-gracious-owl/blob/main/DescriptorFramework.owl (private repository, originally said to be released in October 2021)

eNanoMapper ontology

- URL: github.com/enanomapper/ontologies (open) (1)

NanOn ontology

² As long as GitHub repositories are private, people can request access under a confidentiality agreement with the project coordinator.

- URL: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/NanOn-ontology (proprietary license)

2.2.2 Data models

Each data model comes with a shape expression, written in ShEx, and a query to list all RDF entries that should have the shape for that type. The shape expressions formally describe the data model which helps with validation of the data, both in terms of completeness and in terms of semantics (2).

Namespaces

The SPARQL queries and ShEx described below use shared namespace prefixes, which are listed here once, but should be (partially) included in each of them:

```
PREFIX dc:      <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>
PREFIX foaf:   <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX rdfs:   <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX sbd:    <https://www.sbd4nano.eu/rdf/#>
PREFIX sbdbel: <https://www.sbd4nano.eu/bel/#>
PREFIX xsd:    <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
```

Dataset Descriptor (VOID header)

The dataset descriptor is a Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VOID) header that describes each information source. Each source (like DIAMONDS, eNanoMapper, etc) describes multiple data, models, etc, described by that source. The VOID header provides metadata about the source, allowing us to reproduce tables like Table 1 and Table 2. It follows the *W3C Dataset Descriptions: HCLS Community Profile* (3). The `void.shex` shape expression follows the required fields for a *Summary Level* description.

SPARQL

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/void.rq

ShEx

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/void.shex

Source

General shape underlying Dataset, Database, Assertion, and Model.

ShEx

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/source.shex

```
<resource> {
  dc:source    IRI {1} ;
  rdfs:label   [@en] ;
  dct:license  IRI {1}
}
```

Dataset

SPARQL

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/dataset.rq

```
SELECT ?dataset WHERE {
```


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```
    ?dataset a sbd:Dataset .  
  }
```

ShEx

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/dataset.shex

```
<resource> @ SOURCE:resource AND {  
  a          [sbd:Dataset] ,  
  dc:description xsd:string?,  
  foaf:page    IRI {1,}  
}
```

Database

SPARQL

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/database.rq

```
SELECT ?database WHERE {  
  ?database a sbd:Database .  
}
```

ShEx

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/database.shex

```
<resource> @ SOURCE:resource AND {  
  a          [sbd:Database] ;  
  dc:description xsd:string?,  
  foaf:page    IRI {1,}  
}
```

Model

SPARQL

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/model.rq

```
SELECT ?model WHERE {  
  ?model a sbd:Model .  
}
```

ShEx

Source: github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/shapes/model.shex

```
<resource> @ SOURCE:resource AND {  
  a          [sbd:Model] ,  
  dc:description xsd:string?,  
  foaf:page    IRI {1,}  
}
```

2.2.3 GitHub repositories

To aggregate the information from the various sources, we have set up a series of repositories in the projects in the GitHub organization at github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/. Most of them are currently *private*, meaning that only SbD4Nano project partners have access to it. This does require authentication with a GitHub account.

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The reason is that some data does not have an open license, and all repositories have not been approved to be disseminated yet. The public repositories include:

h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape Central repository. It describes the very draft data model and currently an overview of datasources.

h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-ambit Repository with metadata of the public databases in search.data.enanomap.net/

The following repositories are still internal to the consortium, sometimes because the original source of information does not have an open license:

h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-wp1 Repository contains information sources collected in an Excel spreadsheet by SbD4Nano WP1 (see Section 3)

h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-aopwiki Contains a plugin to get landscape data from AOP-Wiki via the new SPARQL endpoint at aopwiki.rdf.bigcat-bioinformatics.org/ (4)

h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-diamonds Repository with a combination of manually extracted data and a script to extract data from the DIAMONDS spreadsheet.

h2020-sbd4nano/landscape-virtuoso-httpd-docker Repository with Dockerfile and documentation to create a SbD4Nano landscape Virtuoso HTTPD Docker Image.

h2020-sbd4nano/landscape-snorql-extended Repository that contains configurations for the SNORQL graphical interface, which is used in the creation of the Docker Image.

h2020-sbd4nano/LandscapeQueries Repository that contains example SPARQL queries to autopopulate the example query panel in the SNORQL User Interface. Each SPARQL query is added as a .rq file.

2.2.4 Turtle validation with GitHub Actions

Validation of the Turtle syntax of files with data can be validated with the riot tool from the Apache Jena library, conveniently dockerized by Vincent Emonet (Maastricht University Institute for Data Sciences)³. The GitHub Action workflow can be found at github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-landscape/blob/master/.github/workflows/validate.yml and will look like this (YAML format):

```
name: Validation

on:
  push:
  pull_request:

jobs:
  validate-rdf:
    runs-on: ubuntu-latest
    steps:
```

³ <https://github.com/vemonet/jena-riot-action>


```
- uses: actions/checkout@v2
- uses: vemonet/jena-riot-action@v3.14
with:
  input: nanowiki.ttl
```

2.2.4 Querying the landscape with SPARQL

A SPARQL endpoint has been made available on sb4nanolandscape.rdf.bigcat-bioinformatics.org/, using a customized SNORQL software⁴, first used by WikiPathways (5). The data can be queried through this interface to return tables in a new HTML page or as exports in various formats (.tsv, .csv, .json, .xml, etc.). Figure 4 shows the interface and Figure 5 shows the results of the example query presented in Figure 4. Example queries are provided on the right hand side, which are loaded from the public GitHub repository at github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/LandscapeQueries.

2.2.5 Reporting with e-book

UM previously developed a system to write ebooks using a combination of Markdown and scripts that run code, allowing the code and the results to be embedded in the Markdown. This approach is similar in how Jupyter notebooks and RMarkdown books work for Python and the statistical software R. It has been used to demonstrate Java code (egonw.github.io/cdkbook/ about the Chemistry Development Kit) and for SPARQL queries (egonw.github.io/SARS-CoV-2-Queries/ about the SARS-CoV-2 virus and COVID-19). The second approach was reused here.

The methods reused work as follows. Using SPARQL queries developed and described in the earlier sections, data summaries of the landscape are compiled into content for the book. This is done by a combination of shell and Groovy scripts, some of which use the Bacting software to run the SPARQL queries (6), see github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-book (private repository). The SPARQL queries are stored in the /sparql/ folder and the Markdown source in the /src/ folder. Makefiles glue together the scripts.

⁴ <https://github.com/kurtjx/SNORQL>

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SPARQL Endpoint <https://sb4nanolandscape.rdf.bigcat-bioinformatics.org>

SPARQL Query:

```

1 PREFIX sbd: <https://www.sb4nano.eu/rdf/#>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?datasetname ?webpage WHERE {
6   ?dataset a      sbd:Dataset ;
7             rdfs:label ?datasetname .
8   OPTIONAL { ?dataset foaf:page ?webpage . }
9 }
10

```

SPARQL Examples:

<https://github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/Lands>

Type part of the query file name to search for..

- All-Causal-Relationships.rq
- All-Databases-labels.rq
- All-Datasets-names-webpages.rq
- Statistics.rq

Export as:

Figure 4: Screenshot of SPARQL endpoint with a SPARQL query filled in. The SPARQL query retrieves all database names and corresponding URLs.

SPARQL results (33 results)

datasetname	webpage
BAM reference data: XPS raw data of Al-coated titania nanoparticles (JRCNM62001a and JRCNM62002a)	https://zenodo.org/record/4986068
NanoWiki 6	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11897205.v1
FP7 eNanoMapper prototype database	https://search.data.enanmapper.net/projects/enanmapper/
H2020 NanoReg2 - eNanoMapper database	https://search.data.enanmapper.net/projects/nanoreg2/
AOP-Wiki AOP-	https://aopwiki.rdf.bigcat-bioinformatics.org/sparql?default-graph-uri=&query=SELECT+%3FAOP+%3FAOPTitle+%3FAO+%3FAOTitle+WHERE+%7B%0D%0A%20

Figure 5: The resulting table of the executed SPARQL query from Figure 4.

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To make this work for the SbD4Nano landscape a limited number of updates to the code were made, minor in nature (e.g. updating to newer releases of Bacting and Groovy (6)). However, the content of the book is fully done in this project, including the Markdown files in the /src/ folder as well as all SPARQL queries. This gives this book a unique content.

Each SPARQL query can be embedded in the book as well as the output of the SPARQL query, which are shown as tables. The tables can be restricted in the number of rows, improving the flow of the book. The full table is given on a separate page which is available for every SPARQL query.

2.3. Results

2.3.1 Overall statistics

Table 3 shows the overall statistics of information sources on 2022-03-19. Not all this data is publicly available (e.g. because the data is copyrighted by other projects under a non-open license) and includes data collected by WP2 (the causal relationships). The statistics of the public data can be looked up in the SPARQL endpoint, see Section 2.2.4.

source	sourceLabel	databases	datasets	models	relationships	frameworks	guidancetools	guidancedoccs	lcanalyses
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/bcl/	SbD4Nano WP1 Causal Relationships	0	0	0	500	0	0	0	0
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/ECOTOX_DB/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet ECOTOX_DB	22	0	0	0	6	2	0	0
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/HAZARD_TnM/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet HAZARD_TnM	0	0	0	0	10	3	19	19
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/PCEM_DB/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet PCEM_DB	19	0	0	0	4	2	3	3
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/RA_TnM/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet RA_TnM	2	0	0	0	7	4	8	8
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/REGULATION/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet REGULATION	12	0	0	0	2	5	24	24
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/RELEASE_EXPOSURE_T_DbNm/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet RELEASE_EXPOSURE_T_DbNm	14	0	0	0	3	4	14	14
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/RM_TnM/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet RM_TnM	1	0	0	0	0	0	19	19
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/SEAnCBA/	SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet SEAnCBA	4	0	0	0	13	2	0	0
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-nanowiki/models/	ADP-Wiki ADPs	0	0	191	0	0	0	0	0
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-nanowiki/	ADP-Wiki data	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
https://search.data.enanmapper.net/	Datasets hosted at search.data.enanmapper.net	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
https://nanosolveit.eu/resources/tools/services/	NanoSolveIT Tools	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-nanowiki/	NanoWiki v6 causal relationships	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0
https://nanocommons.github.io/datasets/	Overview of open datasets released by NanoSafety Cluster projects	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/w1/bcl_ralch/	SbD4Nano Carbon Nanoforms Causal Relationships	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/smartnanotox/datasets/	SmartNanoTox Transcriptomics datasets	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: number of databases/datasets, models, and casual relationships (assertions) for each source.

2.3.3 Turtle validation

For the *sbd-data-nanowiki* repository (work done as part of WP2, based on the NanoWiki data (7,8)) a GitHub action was set up that uses an RDF validator to check if the Turtle syntax is correct each time one or more commits are pushed. The output may look like that in Figure 6. In this example the one but last action failed (red marker) and the console output was checked for the problem in the Turtle which was an undefined 'dc' namespace. The problem was fixed in the next commit, resulting in valid Turtle again, indicated by the green marker in the most recent action run (at the top of the list).

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The screenshot shows the GitHub Actions interface for the repository `h2020-sbd4nano / sbd-data-nanowiki`. The 'Actions' tab is selected, displaying a list of workflow runs under the heading 'All workflows'. A search bar is present to filter workflow runs. The table below shows the most recent runs:

Event	Status	Branch	Actor
Added missing dc namespace prefix Validation #9: Commit 5de786b pushed by egonw	Success	main	3 minutes ago
Added label and source info Validation #8: Commit 47d932b pushed by egonw	Failure	main	5 minutes ago
Better terms Validation #7: Commit e2f62ef pushed by egonw	Success	main	3 months ago
Any branch, any pull request Validation #6: Commit 290738e pushed by egonw	Success	main	3 months ago

Figure 6: Screenshot of the results of a GitHub action checking the Turtle in a GitHub repository.

2.3.4 Shape Expressions

A *Makefile* was used to check the landscape content against the shape expressions, written in ShEx (2). Output looks like this:

```
Validating the datasets
Running ShEx for https://h2020-sbd4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/s4db1
Errors: 0
Running ShEx for https://h2020-sbd4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/s4db2
Errors: 0
Running ShEx for https://h2020-sbd4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/s4db3
Errors: 0
Running ShEx for https://h2020-sbd4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/s4db4
Errors: 0
```

In the above output no ShEx violations have been found. When the Turtle describing source of information does not match the shape expression, they output will look something like:

```
Validating the assertions
Running ShEx for http://127.0.0.1/mediawiki/index.php/Berg2009_R1
Errors: 2
Running ShEx for http://127.0.0.1/mediawiki/index.php/Berg2009_R2
Errors: 2
Running ShEx for http://127.0.0.1/mediawiki/index.php/Deshpande2005_R1
Errors: 2
Running ShEx for http://127.0.0.1/mediawiki/index.php/Hedberg2010_R1
```


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Competency Question #1: List all data sets

```
PREFIX sbd: <https://www.sbd4nano.eu/rdf/#>

SELECT ?datasetlabel WHERE {
  ?dataset a sbd:Dataset ; rdfs:label ?datasetlabel.
}
```

Competency Question #2: List all data sets with webpage and description

```
PREFIX sbd: <https://www.sbd4nano.eu/rdf/#>
SELECT ?datasetlabel ?webpage ?description WHERE {
  ?dataset a sbd:Dataset ; rdfs:label ?datasetlabel ; dc:description
?description ; foaf:page ?webpage
}
```

Competency Question #3: List number of datasets for each source

```
PREFIX sbd: <https://www.sbd4nano.eu/rdf/#>
SELECT ?source (count (?dataset as ?ndatasets)) WHERE {
  ?dataset a sbd:Dataset ; dc:source ?source .
}
```

2.3.6 The Landscape e-book

Using the approach described in Section 2.2.5 an e-book was created. Figure 7 shows the current contents of the book, while Figure 8 shows how a SPARQL query is embedded and shown in the book, along with a table with the results of that query.

SbD4Nano Resources

This book provides a summary of the semantic landscape of data sources that support the safe-by-design development of nanomaterials. The book is enriched with SPARQL queries, written in the SPARQL query language. To learn more about this query language, consider reading [SPARQLing Biology: a beginners course](#).

Contents

- 1. A Semantic landscape
 - 1.1. General requirements
 - 1.2. Information sources and plugins
 - 1.3. Data sources
 - 1.3.1. Licenses
 - 1.4. Statistics
- 2. Data
 - 2.1. Databases
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- 5. Guidances
 - 5.1. Guidance tools
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 - 6.3. Relationships by outcome
 - 6.4. All relationships

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Figure 7: Table of Content of the SbD4Nano Landscape book, providing an overview of the landscape content.

Data

The landscape found the following datasets and databases.

Databases

SPARQL [sparql/allDatabases.rq](#) (run, edit)

```
PREFIX sbd: <https://www.sb4nano.eu/rdf/#>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?title ?url WHERE {
  ?database a sbd:Database ;
            rdfs:label ?title .
  OPTIONAL { ?database foaf:page ?url }
} ORDER BY ?url
```

This gives us a list of databases, here showing the first 10:

title	url
NanoDesk Knowledge Base	http://130.206.36.124/dataset
ToxChem: Toxic Chemicals Database	http://192.168.1.239:9999/blazegraph/namespace/kb/Aspx
NanoEthicsBank	http://212.235.239.102/node/1958
AMBIT LRI Toolbox	http://ambitlri.ideaconsult.net/
Hazardous Chemical Information System	http://hcis.safeworkaustralia.gov.au
NanoMONITOR Web-Based library	http://library.lifenanomonitor.eu/
NANEX Exposure Scenario Data Library (ESDL)	http://nanex-project.eu/mainpages/exposure-scenarios-db.html
The Nanodatabase	http://nanodb.dk

This table is truncated. See the full table at [sparql/allDatabases.rq](#)

Figure 8: Part of the Landscape e-book showing a SPARQL query to list all databases in the knowledge base.

2.4 Discussion & Conclusion

One of the main challenges in science, and this includes the fields of risk governance and nanosafety research is to have FAIR access to relevant knowledge. FAIR data is quite established, but data important to our research is scattered over many different research output types. This became particularly clear from the results of Deliverable D1.1. Therefore, when we need to build a sustainable platform to support research in our research field, we have to establish a platform that is capable of integrating many different data sources. Fortunately, a combination of semantic web technologies, FAIR research output principles and associated efforts, allowed us to implement our foundation of the approach sketched in Figure 3. We have developed a modular platform that can pull in data and metadata from diverse sources, unify this with semantic web approaches (RDF, ontologies, and shape expressions), and make this accessible as FAIR data itself (SPARQL). The next section shows this platform in action for the data aggregated in Deliverable D1.1.

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3. RDF for Deliverable D1.1

This section requires access to embargoed material. Reviewers can request access by contacting the project coordinator.

3.1 Introduction

As one of the first steps in the SbD4Nano project, based on the tools and methods inventory in the NanoRisk Governance Portal of the EU NMBP-13 Gov4Nano project, an overview was created of the available resources that can be useful for a Safe-by-Design (SbD) approach for engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) and nano-enabled products (NEPs). This was done under Task T1.1 and reported on in SbD4Nano Deliverable D1.1. An exhaustive evaluation of these resources, including databases, models and documents was performed, followed by a resource gap analysis.

The overview of available resources was created in an Excel sheet (see Figure 9). This is common practice in (European) projects, but since these excel files are often not disseminated, this means the same exercise has to be performed at the start of each project. As indicated in Section 2, the use of semantic web technologies enables us to combine information from many different sources to create a knowledge graph like the Semantic Bioactivity Landscape.

In this section we describe the process of converting the Excel sheet from D1.1 to the Resource Description Framework (RDF).

Figure 9: Excel sheet with overview of the available resources that can be useful for SbD approaches

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3.2 Method

The CSV file was converted to RDF using a script. The script was written in a Jupyter Notebook in Python using the Pandas and RDFlib Libraries. It was made available in a github repository and can be found here (NB. currently the repository is still private): github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd-data-wp1/blob/main/create_ttl_wp1_rdflib.ipynb

In the following paragraphs the steps in the script will be explained.

After saving the excel file as a csv file, the first step was to read the information from the excel to a pandas dataframe (df). As you can see in Figure 9, the first few lines of the Excel contain header information and need to be excluded from the df.

Although the excel file was carefully curated, it still contains unexpected values. The next step was therefore to perform data normalization. For example, the excel sheet contains values like “1. Yes”, “2. No” and “3. Partly”. Though the numbering of these values makes sense in the excel, for the RDF the numbers do not have added value and are therefore stripped from the strings.

A mapping was created from the column names to sbd-ontology terms. An example of such a mapping can be found in the following snippet of code:

```
col_dict = {"ToolType": "Type of tool", "OutputCertainty": "Tool type/ Output certainty",  
"ApplicationDomain": "Application domain", "InterfaceType": "Data sharability/ Stand alone  
application", "ExposureRoutes": "Applicable routes of exposure",  
"ApplicableRnIPhase": "Applicable R&I phase", "ApplicablePopulation": "Applicable  
population", "ApplicableProduct": "Applicable products with EU regulations",  
"ApplicableMaterial": "Applicable material", "LifeCycleStage": "Applicable life cycle  
stage"}
```

Now that the data is normalized and the columns mapped we can start building the graph which will later be used to output the RDF. For this we use the RDFlib Library.

First we initiate a graph:

```
g = Graph()
```

Then, using the `.bind` functionalization, we indicate which namespaces we want to use:

```
g.bind("dc", DC)  
g.bind("rdfs", RDFS)  
g.bind("sbd", sbd)  
...
```

The ontologies used in developing the RDF along with their prefixes are:

```
prefix dc: IRI http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/  
prefix dcterms: IRI http://purl.org/dc/terms/  
prefix foaf: IRI http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/  
prefix kb: IRI https://h2020-sbd4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/  
prefix ncit: IRI http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT
```


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```
prefix rdfs: IRI http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
prefix sbd: IRI https://www.sb4nano.eu/rdf/#
prefix void: IRI http://rdfs.org/ns/void#
```

After defining the ontologies we want to use, we can start adding triples to the graph using the `.add` command. Here are four example triples:

```
g.add((sbd.Yes, RDF.type, ncit.C49488))
g.add((sbd.Yes, RDFS.label, Literal("Yes")))
g.add((sbd.No, RDF.type, ncit.C49487))
g.add((sbd.No, RDFS.label, Literal("No")))
```

As can be seen in these examples, you need three pieces of information which make up the triple: the subject, predicate and object. The object can be an URIRef, but also a Literal or a Blank node.

The script loops over the columns, e.g. the columns in the earlier defined `col_dict`, and adds the information to the graph in the form of triples. Columns currently taken into account by the script are the column #, Name, Owner of the tool, URL, Nanospecific, Type of tool, Data shareability/ Stand alone application, Tool type/ Output certainty, Application domain, Applicable routes of exposure, Applicable R&I phase, Applicable life cycle stage, Applicable population, Applicable products with EU regulations, Applicable material, Short description of tool and Short description/link of tool.

If a column does not contain information for a certain tool it is skipped.

The final step of the script is to print the graph to RDF using the `.serialize` command. This can be done using various syntaxes (turtle, rdf/xml, n3, n-triples, trix, JSON-LD, etc.). The simplest format is n-triples, which is a triple-per-line format. Here we print in the Notation3 (“n3”) format using the following command:

```
g.serialize(format='n3',destination="wp1_full_table.ttl")
```

3.3 Results

The output of the script is almost 6000 lines of RDF. In this section we look at some of the output.

3.3.1 Example triples

In the previous section we saw four example triples were added to the graph. The output for these examples looks as follows:

```
sbd:Yes          a          ncit:C49488          ;
  rdfs:label "Yes" .

sbd:No          a          ncit:C49487          ;
  rdfs:label "No" .
```


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3.3.2 Dataset Description

The different tabs in the spreadsheet are seen as different data sources. The sources are described as a `void:DatasetDescription`. The triples contain information about the source, the title and the page. An example is shown below:

```
<https://h2020-sbd4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/> a
void:DatasetDescription ;
    dc:source "210326_Nano modeling tools inventory - V4.xlsx" ;
    dcterms:title "SbD4Nano WP1 Sheet ECOTOX_DB" ;
    foaf:page
<https://itene.sharepoint.com/:x:/r/sites/SbD4Nano/WP/WP1/Deliverables%20and%20Milestones/D1.1.%20Resource%20gap%20analysis/210326_Nano%20modeling%20tools%20inventory%20-%20V4.xlsx?d=w7da492120cab4e3ea71f2a6cb2de33a7&csf=1&web=1&e=2SMaGc> .
```

3.3.3 RDF per resource

Each tab contains a number of resources (289 in total). All resources are annotated as a `sbd:Resource`. These resources can be anything from a Database to a Guidance tool or document, from a Framework to Risk Screening or a Life cycle assessment and several others. These are all `sbd:ToolType`'s and are defined as follows:

```
sbd:Database a sbd:ToolType ;
    rdfs:label "Database" .
```

This way you can use a SPARQL query to return all `sdb:ToolTypes`. `ToolType` is a property of the resources and the content is extracted from one of the columns in the spreadsheet. There are 10 columns which result in a `sbd:Property` for example:

```
sbd:ToolType a sbd:Property .
sbd:ApplicableProduct a sbd:Property .
```

These properties have standardized values, which are taken from the excel and described in the `sbd` namespace. Using a SPARQL query one can extract the values of the properties:

```
PREFIX sbd: <https://www.sbd4nano.eu/rdf/#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>

SELECT DISTINCT ?property ?propertyValue ?valueLabel
WHERE {
    ?property a sbd:Property .
    ?propertyValue a ?property ;
        rdfs:label ?valueLabel .
} ORDER BY ?property
```

By combining all different elements discussed so far we can describe the resources. Here we show the example of `eNanoMapper`, which includes the tool type, the name as a label, a description, the website, the tool owner and properties like the application domain or if the tool is nano-specific.

```
kb:ECOTOX_DB_28.0 a sbd:Database,
    sbd:Framework,
    sbd:Resource ;
```


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```
rdfs:label "eNanoMapper"@en ;
dc:description "A database and ontology framework for design and safety assessment
of nanomaterials. Open source database and web application. Data can be imported as
Excel templates, RDF, OECD OHT or SQL and exported as ISA-JSON, RDF or XLSX. Integrated
with data analysis and search tools (free text, chemistry, semantic)."@en ;
dc:source <https://h2020-sbd4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/> ;
foaf:page <http://search.data.enanmapper.net> ;
sbd:hasApplicableRnIPhase sbd:DesignPhase ;
sbd:hasApplicationDomain sbd:HazardAssessment,
sbd:MaterialCharacterization ;
sbd:hasLifeCycleStage sbd:RnDaoSynthesis ;
sbd:hasOutputCertainty sbd:Quantitative ;
sbd:interfaceType sbd:ProgramOrAutomated ;
sbd:nanospecific sbd:Yes ;
sbd:toolOwner "Ideaconsult Ltd."@en .
```

3.4 Discussion

By converting the overview of the available resources from Deliverable D1.1 to RDF, we increase the FAIRness of the data. Of the FAIR principles especially the interoperability is increased by annotating all instances with ontologies. As indicated in Section 3.2, many columns from the spreadsheet are already converted to RDF. However, there are currently 19 columns that are not converted to RDF. This is because these are only filled out for a few resources. Nevertheless it is the goal to add these columns to the script during the remainder of the project.

3.5 Conclusions

In this section we describe the conversion to RDF of a spreadsheet containing the available resources that can be useful for a Safe-by-Design (SbD) approach for engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) and nano-enabled products (NEPs). A Python script was written in a Jupyter Notebook using the Pandas and RDFlib Libraries. The output of the script is almost 6000 lines of RDF which describe the 289 resources with information like the tool type, the name as a label, a description, the website, the tool owner and properties like the application domain or if the tool is nano-specific. The RDF is made available in the landscape SPARQL endpoint. This allows for querying the RDF to retrieve data and allows the user to find a resource that fits their needs. Something that can also be done through the e-infrastructure (see Section 7).

4. Implementation of atena.urv.cat

4.1 Introduction

Atena is a web site accessed through atena.urv.cat which acts as a document repository service.

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The website is a centralized repository of nanotechnology article references, ordered and classified using two concepts:

- Groups: Sets of keys
- Keys: concrete concepts of the nanotechnology field, like Nanoclay. A Key can only belong to one Group.

4.2 Method

This repository is fed using three data sources:

- Google Scholar. Automatically. Once a week.
- Scopus. Automatically. Once a week.
- Article references sent by users by e-mail.

Keys and groups can be manually deleted or inserted by the administrative staff.

To feed the database, with new content requested by users, it is first needed to send a request to the e-mail account (sbd4nano@urv.cat) with the subject User registration. Then, the information you want to include in the repository must be introduced in an Excel file and be sent to the same e-mail account. The modification of the repository can take some days since it is manually done.

Requirements for the Excel file:

- Only one Excel file is supported per e-mail.
- The Excel file must have only one sheet.
- Each row must have a value.
- No empty rows are allowed.
- The first row of this Excel file must have the following columns names:
 - title: main title of the article entrance
 - author: author or authors of the articles
 - year: publication year. It must be a number, like 2021 or 2001
 - source: Name of the publication journal. For example “Nature”
 - link: URL or link to the article
 - abstract: the abstract of the article
 - key: Check the web page, left site.

All keys are valid, except the keys that are year filters. For example “Gar barrier”. Use exactly the same name, with the same capital letters and spaces. Do not use “.” or “,”. If you miss any key, please contact the administrator of the site to add the corresponding key before sending any mail.

In the case that the article can be classified using more than one key, the row has to be duplicated, changing only the key column value. Consequently, if the article belongs to three keys, you have to triplicate the article entry, and so on.

Once one has sent the mail to sbd4nano@urv.cat, in around 20 minutes a mail response will be received. Through this email response you will be informed on how the process has finished, and if any error has been found.

If you wish to have an Excel file example, please send an email to sbd4nano@urv.cat with the subject Excel example.

4.3 Results and Discussion

The main page of the web service is the following:

You can make a search in a “Google style” in the “Search data” input text box, or you can click on any of the most popular keys below the input text box.

On the other hand, you can click on “Datasets” (top – right) to see an ordered and classified set of article references as follows:

The screenshot shows the 'Datasets' page of the SbD Nano database. On the left, there is a sidebar with 'Groups' (nanoparticles: 199, properties: 169, safety: 225) and 'Keys' (years from 2002 to 2021, Citotoxicity, Gas barrier). The main content area shows a search bar, a '485 datasets found' result, and a list of articles with titles and authors. The 'Order by' dropdown is set to 'Last Modified'.

On the left side, the “groups” of keys are visible, and below the “most popular” keys. In this case, most of the keys are the publication years, because the first keys are the most referenced ones. To see the complete list of keys you only need to click on “Show More Keys”, and all keys will be shown.

Using the keys and groups you can make very specific searches in the database. For example, in the following screenshot, the “2006” key was clicked. For that case, there are 19 datasets containing articles references of the year 2006.

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The screenshot shows the 'Datasets' page on the Sbd Nano website. A search bar at the top right contains the text 'Search datasets...'. Below the search bar, it displays '19 datasets found' and an 'Order by: Last Modified' dropdown menu. A filter for the year '2006' is applied. The left sidebar shows a list of 'Keys' with '2006' selected. The main content area lists three articles with their titles and authors.

2006 19

- Abrasion resistance 1
- Carbon nanofiber 1
- Consumer safety 1
- Electromagnetic inte... 1
- Environmental safety 1
- Exposure 1
- Gas barrier 1
- Graphene 1
- Nanoclay 1

19 datasets found Order by: Last Modified

Keys: 2006 ✕

Numerical and experimental analysis of different ventilation systems in deep ...
MT Parra, JM Villafraña, F Castro, C Mendez - Building and Environment, 2006 - Elsevier The ventilation system plays an essential role in underground workings. On an...
[link](#)

Determining the size and shape dependence of gold nanoparticle uptake into ma...
BD Chithrani, AA Ghazani, WCW Chan - Nano letters, 2006 - ACS Publications We investigated the intracellular uptake of different sized and shaped colloidal gold nanoparticles...
[link](#)

Toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics of ochratoxin A, an update
D Ringot, A Chango, YJ Schneider... - Chemo-biological ..., 2006 - Elsevier Ochratoxin A (OTA) is a mycotoxin produced by fungi of two genera: Penicillium and Aspergillus. OTA has...
[link](#)

You can also apply more filters, by clicking, for instance, on another key: Nanoclay. As a result, one gets a combined filter showing only articles matching “2006” and “Nanoclay”.

Finally, by clicking in the title of the article reference, more information appears related to the article entry:

The screenshot shows the article page for 'Investigation of the mechanical properties of DGEBA-based epoxy resin with nanoclay additives'. The left sidebar shows the organization 'sbd4nano' with 0 followers and social media links for Twitter and Facebook. The main content area displays the article title, authors (B Qi, QX Zhang, M Bainnister, YW Mai), and a brief abstract. Below the abstract, there are sections for 'Keys' (2006, Nanoclay) and 'Additional Info' which includes a table with fields like Source and Origin.

Organizations / sbd4nano / Investigation of the...

Investigation of the mechanical properties of DGEBA-based epoxy resin with nanoclay additives

Followers: 0

Organization: sbd4nano
There is no description for this organization

Social: Twitter, Facebook

Investigation of the mechanical properties of DGEBA-based epoxy resin with nanoclay additives

B Qi, QX Zhang, M Bainnister, YW Mai - Composite structures, 2006 - Elsevier

The present study investigated the effect of nanoclay additives on the mechanical properties of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin. The resin was cured with diethyltoluene diamine (DETD) hardener and four material variations produced through the ...

Keys: 2006 Nanoclay

Additional Info

Field	Value
Source	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263822306001796
Origin	Google Scholar

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This page shows the title of the article and in the row below the authors, complementary information, the publication year and finally the name of the journal.

Depending on the origin of the information stored in the repository, below this additional information appears as well:

- If the origin is mail: The information set by the user in the “abstract” field/column.
- If the origin is Google Scholar: The lines where the “keys” were found.
- If the origin is Scopus: The complete abstract of the article.

Below the previous information, the keys that belong to the article are shown. And finally, in Additional Info, the link is shown of the article (Source), and the Origin of this article, in this case “Google Scholar”, but it can also be “Mail” or “Scopus” mentioned before.

4.4 Conclusions

A new tool has been developed to easily query information of nanocompounds published in scientific papers. The system queries new documents once a week. The repository is publically available at atena.urv.cat.

5. Exposure triples in TNO’s DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point

5.1 Introduction

In order to apply a Safe-by-Design approach, as a bare minimum, it is important a) to at least understand which characteristics of the design are able to influence exposure and hazard (and thus effect risk) and b) to be able to hypothesize in what direction (increased or decreased) they need to be changed. For example, if one knows that the dustiness of a nanomaterial is positively correlated with the exposure and exposure is positively correlated with risk, then one can hypothesize that to reduce the risk of a certain design one could try to reduce the corresponding exposure and to minimize the exposure one could try to reduce the dustiness of the nanomaterial. One can continue this line of reasoning until one finds a nanomaterial property (e.g. bulk density, aspect ratio) that can be affected by changing the nanomaterial. To this end, it is important to establish a network of known influences between factors from nanomaterial properties via intermediate factors towards exposure. Obviously, there is more needed for a Safe-by-Design approach, but the work in this section is focussed purely on uncovering the basic influence relationships relevant to exposure.

Therefore, to hypothesize potential causal effects, we aim to create a repository of triplets that indicate causal relations between factors. In this context, a factor represents a concept that has relevance and meaning, such as a nanomaterial property, a biological process, a measurable effect or scorable entity.

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Such factors could be represented as nodes in an influence network and the relationship between factors as edges in that network. In this work, we have restricted ourselves to factors relevant to exposure. Work package 2 will continue the development of these triples for other areas relevant for safe-by-design approaches.

To share this knowledge with a wider community within as well as outside the SbD4Nano project two lines of work are needed to be done, i.e. A) **content-wise**: utilize domain knowledge, literature and resources to define the relevant factors and their influences and B) **technically**: convert the content into triples and set-up the infrastructure (a FDP and Triple-Store) to make them available to others. These approaches are further explained in the following two sections. The final section concludes this section with a discussion.

5.2 Content-wise Method and Results

To create the content, we utilized our domain knowledge and expertise in the field of exposure and nano-materials, studied relevant literature, and examined the underlying structures of exposure models and exposure resources (captured in the resources excel sheets from Deliverable D1.1). The first step was to determine which factors have any known relevance with exposure. This knowledge was formalized in an excel sheet that captured the name of the factor, a link to external ontology term, whether there is a relationship with exposure and/or the type/directionality of that relationship (positive, negative, unknown) and the underlying resources. These factors were also grouped by their type of exposure determinant (e.g. substance emission potential, activity emission potential, dilution, local controls and immission potential). The left side of Figure 10 illustrates this excel sheet with the colors indicating the grouping.

Figure 10. Overall view illustrating the creation of the exposure knowledge content from creating a list of relevant factors (left) towards creation of an organized list of relationships between factors (right). Left

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side shows a table with all relevant factors on the rows, including information about underlying ontological terms, the presence of an effect and/or its directionality and underlying resources. Right side shows rows of paths, originating on the left via intermediate factors in the middle, ultimately ending with exposure on the right. The directionality of each relation indicated in green for positive and red for negative directionality.

By studying the underlying resources deeper, the relationships between the underlying intermediate factors were unraveled, creating a set of relationships between two factors (and their directionality) which could be organized into influence paths from left to right, for each factor (on the left) via intermediate factors (in the middle) up to exposure (on the right). These relationships and paths are illustrated on the right side of Figure 10.

5.3 Technical Method and Results

Figure 11 illustrates schematically the steps taken to convert the content described in Section 5.2 into a technical infrastructure that allows both humans to find and investigate the information using a browser, while simultaneously allowing external IT-systems to interact with the exact same information via SPARQL interactions. The green boxes describe the steps taken in Section 5.2 aimed at creating the content illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 11. Schematic diagram illustrating how information flows from the content-wise method (green boxes on the left) into the technical method (blue boxes on the right) towards the benefit of both human operators as well as IT-systems (fully on the right).

“WebProtégé is an ontology development environment for the Web that makes it easy to create, upload, modify, and share ontologies for collaborative viewing and editing.” (9). We used WebProtege to manually create RDF Triples from the information captured in the excel sheets. WebProtege allows our experts to keep on managing all exposure related information in RDF format but in a human-friendly web-based tool. Figure 12 shows a screenshot of WebProtege with an inset panel that shows graphically the influence diagram from Coagulation to Exposure. In WebProtege, all factors are available as a list of individuals shown (and searchable) on the left. In this example, Coagulation was selected, which is indicated by the blue highlight. In the middle panel all RDF-based information captured about the selected

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individual/factor (here: Coagulation) is shown and editable as well. This information contains annotation-like information such as the label, description, synonyms, references to other ontological terms and links to related wikipathways and sources. The relational information is captured under “Relationships” indicating a negative correlation with Exposure as well as a negative correlation with Dustiness.⁵ WebProtégé also allows a graphical depiction of the relationships which is shown in the inset panel of Figure 12. This shows that Dustiness itself has a positive correlation with exposure.

Figure 12. Screenshot of WebProtégé showing on the left the list of individuals (factors), in the middle the information captured for a chosen individual (here: coagulation) and in the inset-panel on the right a graphical diagram of the influence relations from “Coagulation” via “Dustiness” to “Exposure”.

“GraphDB is an enterprise ready Semantic Graph Database, compliant with W3C Standards. Semantic graph databases (also called RDF triple stores) provide the core infrastructure for solutions where modelling agility, data integration, relationship exploration and cross-enterprise data publishing and consumption are important.”⁶. We used GraphDB to set up an RDF TripleStore that stores the RDF triples

⁵ For this particular situation one could hypothesize that the negative correlation found between Coagulation and Exposure may be an indirect effect that can be explained by the direct effects of Coagulation on Dustiness and Dustiness on Exposure. However, such hypotheses are left to the interpretation of experts that are using the RDF information and are not in scope for this deliverable. Where possible, we aim to describe observations with direct effects rather than indirect effects to avoid redundant information.

⁶ GraphDB, <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

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created in WebProtege and make them machine-readable by providing a corresponding SPARQL endpoint. GraphDB also provides a web interface for human exploration, visualization and interaction with the triples. Figure 13 illustrates the GraphDB web interface. Users can define SPARQL queries and see the results. Here we show a SPARQL query to obtain information concerning “Coagulation” and the resulting triples are shown in the bottom table of Figure 13. Users can also create network visualizations, a.k.a. visual “graphs” (see inset panel in Figure 13). This inset panel shows both upstream- (“Capillary force”, “van der Waals force” and “Electrostatic force”) as well as downstream factors of Coagulation (“Dustiness” and “Exposure”).

Figure 13. Screenshot of our GraphDB website showing the querying interface with the SPARQL query in the top and the resulting triples in the bottom table. In the inset-panel on the right a graphical diagram of the influence relations from “Coagulation” are visualized.

“A FAIR Data Point (sometimes abbreviated to FDP) is the realisation of the vision of a group of authors of the original paper on FAIR on how (meta)data could be presented on the web using existing standards, and without the need of APIs.

A FAIR Data Point ultimately stores information about data sets, which is the definition of metadata. And just like the webserver in the WWW in the beginning of the 1990s brought the power of publishing text to anyone, a FAIR data point aims to give anyone the power of putting their own data on the web.

The system is called a FAIR data point because it takes care of a lot of the issues that need to be taken care of to make data FAIR; especially with the metadata needed for Findability and Reusability, and a uniform open way of Accessing the data. The FAIR data point also addresses the Interoperability of the

metadata it stores, but it leaves the Interoperability aspects for the data itself to the data provider.”, from www.fairdatapoint.org (10).

We have set up a FAIR Data Point according to the Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences (DTL) specifications, the TNO DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point: diamonds.tno.nl/fairdatapoint. We created a “catalog”, a “dataset” and a “distribution” (i.e. essential meta-data components for a FAIR Data Point) describing the information available in our GraphDB Exposure triplestore. This way, users can find our information via the web-based access of the FDP (See Figure 14 for a screenshot). At the same time, the exact same meta-data information captured by our FDP is also made available for machines by capturing and exposing the meta-data information itself in RDF as well. Our FDP also contains a reference to our GraphDB Exposure triplestore so that if our meta-data information is found to be of interest, users are redirected to the actual exposure triples in our triplestore.

All FDPs are monitored by a FAIR Data Point index (home.fairdatapoint.org/) including our FDP and made findable by its corresponding website. At this website people can do a search for useful information in all meta-data information over all FDPs, thus making our exposure triples findable by everyone.

The screenshot shows the 'Factors and influences relevant for exposure' page on the TNO DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point website. The page features a breadcrumb trail: 'TNO DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point / Exposure / Factors and influences relevant for ex...'. The main content area is titled 'Factors and influences relevant for exposure' and includes a description: 'A dataset containing information about factors and the influences they have on each other relevant to exposure. Factors include (nano-)material characteristics, biological/physical properties and effects and processes.' Below this, there is a 'Distributions' section with a 'SPARQL distribution' card showing 'Issued 11-03-2022', 'Modified 11-03-2022', and 'Media Type application/sparql-results+json'. On the right side, there is a metadata sidebar with fields: 'Metadata Issued' (11-03-2022), 'Metadata Modified' (11-03-2022), 'Conforms to' (Dataset Profile), 'Version' (1), 'Language' (en.html), 'License' (cc-by-nc-nd3.0), 'Theme' (Q1384726, Q25536342, Q967847), 'Keyword' (exposure (environmental influence), nanomaterial, toxin exposure), and 'Download RDF' (ttl, rdf+xml, json-ld).

Figure 14. Screenshot of TNO DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point showing the human readable metadata information that can be explored via a web browser but which is also machine-readable in RDF. This FAIR Data Point describes and points users to our GraphDB triplestore.

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5.4 Conclusions

We have created a wealth of information about important factors and their interrelationships that can ultimately influence exposure (and thus influence risk). This information has been curated, organized and digitized in the form of RDF triples. The management and accessibility of this valuable information has been supported by creating an underlying IT-infrastructure, consisting of deployment and configuration of our own instances of WebProtege, GraphDB, and a FAIR Data Point. This allows new content to continue to grow constantly, while providing instant access to that growing pool of information for both human users (e.g. scientists, regulators, companies) as well as external IT-systems (e.g. SbD4Nano eInfrastructure). With this work, we believe we have created a valuable contribution to the Semantic Bioactivity landscape and created a stepping stone for future Safe-by-Design approaches.

6. Nanosafety Data Interface

The NanoSafety Data Interface (11) available at search.data.enanomapper.net/ provides a user-friendly access to the aggregated search index of the (sub)set of eNanoMapper database instances. An eNanoMapper database instance is an installation of AMBIT software (ambit.sf.net), which implements the eNanoMapper data model (12). Usually consists of data from individual nanosafety projects and may be protected by role-based access to keep data confidential. At the moment of writing there are 18 eNanoMapper database instances and 16 project specific aggregated views including one for SbD4Nano - eNanoMapper database at search.data.enanomapper.net/projects/sbd4nano. The SbD4Nano - eNanoMapper database provides an aggregated view to NANoREG. Nanoreg2, SANOWORK, Omics metadata, caNanoLab and public eNanoMapper database instances. More projects will be included based on pairwise agreements between projects.

Figure 15: Overview of SbD4Nano - eNanoMapper database content in terms of data available for specific NM categories. Categorization of NMs is visualized in line with the current annotation of the data (based on eNanoMapper ontology).

A User guide is available at search.data.enanomapper.net/projects/sbd4nano/search_tutorial/. Programmatic access (REST API) is available at api.ideaconsult.net and supports standard authentication and authorization protocols (API Key and OAuth2), which are used by the SbD4Nano e-infrastructure (WP5). Data entry is facilitated by an online template generator (Template Wizard), which has accumulated more than 50 Excel templates for a variety of physicochemical, ecotoxicity and toxicity assays. The data entry files are subject to the FAIRification workflow (13), which includes multi-step ontology matching and annotation and finally import into eNanoMapper database instance.

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Figure 16: An overview of data and study types. The number of data points for each type of data is indicated above the columns in the first panel. The categories on X axis are endpoints categories as defined in OECD Harmonized Templates (e.g. Particle size distribution- Granulometry), with additional categories based on eNanoMapper ontology introduced where there is no match in the OECD HT (e.g. Cell viability).

To demonstrate programmatic access, a Jupyter notebook is added at github.com/h2020-sbd4nano/sbd4nano-notebooks/blob/main/summaries.ipynb (private repository).

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7. Integration of RDF into the e-infrastructure

7.1 Introduction

A public version of the e-infrastructure is available (during the project at sb4nano.azurewebsites.net) where data from the landscape described in Section 2 is made available to human users in a convenient format. Here they can find the information sources to use during their SbD process.

7.2 Method

The Turtle file (wp1_full_table.ttl) from the landscape repository is processed by a parser to generate and cache the data as a table.

The parser was created using the ANTLR parser generator tool, this generator can be used to convert the Turtle grammar derived from (<http://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/#sec-grammar-grammar>) into a parser. This parser is then used in the e-infrastructure to convert the turtle file into a table to be used in the e-infrastructure.

```

@prefix dc: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/> .
@prefix dcterm: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix kb: <https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/> .
@prefix ncit: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ncit/> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix sbd: <https://www.sb4nano.eu/rdf/#> .
@prefix void: <http://rdfs.org/ns/void#> .

kb:ECOTOX_DB_28.0 a sbd:Database, sbd:Framework, sbd:Resource ;
  rdfs:label "enanomapper" ;
  dc:description "A database and ontology framework for design and safety assessment of nanomaterials. Open source database and web application. Data can be imported as Excel templates, RDF, OECD OHT or SQL and exported as ISA-JSON, RDF or XLSX. Integrated with data analysis and search tools (free text, chemistry, semantic).";
  dc:source <https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/> ;
  foaf:page <http://search.data.enanomapper.net/> ;
  sbd:hasApplicableMaterial sbd:DesignPhase ;
  sbd:hasApplicableDomain sbd:MaterialCharacterization ;
  sbd:hasApplicableRoute sbd:RnDaoSynthesis ;
  sbd:hasOutputCertainty sbd:Quantitative ;
  sbd:interFaceType sbd:ProgramOrAutomated ;
  sbd:nanospecific sbd:Yes ;
  sbd:toolOwner "Ideconsult Ltd." .

kb:ECOTOX_DB_29.0 a sbd:DatabaseManagement, sbd:Resource ;
  rdfs:label "toxflow" ;
  dc:description ""web application for enrichment analysis of omics data (GSVA, gene set variation analysis) and predictive read-across modeling of toxicity. If physicochemical and omics data on a nanoparticle are available, both techniques can be applied in sequential order: users can filter omics data using enrichment scores and incorporate their findings into a correlation-based read-across technique for predicting a toxicity index based on analogs. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29281278 the link to the tool (http://at7.sbd.db.129.3838/toxflow) does not work"" ;
  dc:source <https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/> ;
  foaf:page <https://toxflow.jagpot.org/> ;
  sbd:hasApplicableMaterial sbd:LiquidDispersion, sbd:PowderedNonSphericalParticulate, sbd:PowderedSphericalParticulate ;
  sbd:hasApplicableRoute sbd:ChemicalSubstances ;
  sbd:hasApplicableDesignPhase sbd:DesignPhase ;
  sbd:hasApplicableDomain sbd:HazardAssessment ;
  sbd:hasExposureRoutes sbd:AllRoutes ;
  sbd:hasLifeCycleStage sbd:RnDaoSynthesis ;
  sbd:interFaceType sbd:WebTool ;
  sbd:nanospecific sbd:Partly ;
  sbd:toolOwner "enanomapper" .

kb:ECOTOX_DB_30.0 a sbd:DatabaseManagement, sbd:Resource ;
  rdfs:label "Jagpot Quattro" ;
  dc:description "The web application Jagpot Quattro allows building QSAR models and using them for predictions. As an input, Jagpot Quattro uses data available from the enanomapper database. After preprocessing, transforming and preparing the datasets, various modeling algorithms can be applied." ;
  dc:source <https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/> ;

```


a	description	source	title	page
label	hasApplicableMaterial		hasApplicablePopulation	
	hasApplicableRoute	hasLifeCycleStage	hasOutputCertainty	interFaceType
	nanospecific	toolOwner		
kb:ECOTOX_DB_28.0 Database, Framework, Resource	A database and ontology framework for design and safety assessment of nanomaterials. Open source database and web application. Data can be imported as Excel templates, RDF, OECD OHT or SQL and exported as ISA-JSON, RDF or XLSX. Integrated with data analysis and search tools (free text, chemistry, semantic).	https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/http://search.data.enanomapper.net	eNanoMapper	
Yes	DesignPhase	RnDaoSynthesis	HazardAssessment, MaterialCharacterization	ProgramOrAutomated
kb:ECOTOX_DB_29.0 DatabaseManagement, Resource	users can filter omics data using enrichment scores and incorporate their findings into a correlation-based read-across technique for predicting a toxicity index based on analogs. https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/https://toxflow.jagpot.org/	toxflow	Quantitative	
PowderedNonSphericalParticulate, PowderedSphericalParticulate	HazardAssessment	AllRoutes	RnDaoSynthesis	ChemicalSubstances DesignPhase WebTool
Partly	eNanoMapper			
kb:ECOTOX_DB_30.0 DatabaseManagement, Resource	The web application Jagpot Quattro allows building QSAR models and using them for predictions. As an input, Jagpot Quattro uses data available from the eNanoMapper database. After preprocessing, transforming and preparing the datasets, various modeling algorithms can be applied.	https://www.jagpot.org/https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/https://github.com/enanomapper/RRegrs	eNanoMapper	Quantitative
Jagpot Quattro	PowderedSphericalParticulate	AllRoutes	RnDaoSynthesis	Quantitative
DesignPhase	HazardAssessment	AllRoutes	eNanoMapper	
WebTool	No			
kb:ECOTOX_DB_31.0 DatabaseManagement, Resource	AnRPackageForComputerAidedModelSelectionWithMultipleRegressionModels.JournalOfChemInformSci	https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/https://github.com/enanomapper/RRegrs		
AllRoutes	DesignPhase	RnDaoSynthesis	HazardAssessment, MaterialCharacterization	ProgramOrAutomated
Partly	eNanoMapper			
kb:ECOTOX_DB_32.0 Database, Resource	A data sharing portal designed to facilitate information sharing across the international biomedical nanotechnology research community to expedite and validate the use of nanotechnology in biomedicine	https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/https://canolab.nci.nih.gov/caNanoLab/#	caNanoLab	DesignPhase
	ChemicalSubstances, Drugs			
MaterialCharacterization	Yes	National Cancer Institute, Center for Biomedical Informatics & Information Technology		
kb:ECOTOX_DB_33.0 DatabaseManagement, Resource	"	https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/http://nano.biobyte.de/	INSiE NANO (Integrated Network of Systems biology Effects of nanomaterials)	
Partly	GeneralPopulation		ChemicalSubstances, Drugs	DesignPhase
HazardAssessment	AllRoutes		RnDaoSynthesis, Use Quantitative	WebTool
kb:ECOTOX_DB_34.0 Database, Resource	"/openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/161/"	https://h2020-sb4nano.github.io/sbd-data-landscape/wp1/ECOTOX_DB/https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/161/	Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database	

In the e-infrastructure this resulting table is loaded and the selected columns are presented to the user.

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The document repository described in Section 4 and hosted at <https://atena.urv.cat> is embedded into the e-infrastructure using a HTML iframe. The infrastructure generates the following HTML code for this:

```

<iframe src="https://atena.urv.cat/dataset" title="NanoDesk repository">
</iframe>

```

7.3 Results and Discussion

By selecting “Nano modelling tools inventory” on the SbD resources page of the e-infrastructure an overview is presented in a table view. By using the available filters under the Filter button, the user can restrict the results to their specific case.

SbD4Nano												
SbD resources Guidelines Success stories Log in												
Filter Clear filter												
1 2 3 4 5 6												
Label & owner	Exposure Routes	LifeCycle Stage	Applicable Material	Type	interface	Output Certainty	Applicable Product	Applicable RnI/Phase	nanospecific	Population	Description	Application Domain
Consepro Nano Tool Owner: RIVM	Inhalation only	Use	Liquid dispersion	Resource, Numerical estimate values	Web-tool	Quantitative	Chemical substances, Biocides	Design phase	Yes	Consumer		
Explorative particle flow analysis (PFA) Owner: Chalmers University of Technology		Use, Manufacturing, End-of-Life, R&D and/or synthesis	Powdered spherical particulate, Powdered non-spherical particulate, Liquid dispersion	Numerical/Values, Resource	Program / Automated	Quantitative	Food labelling, Medical devices, Cosmetic products, Food contact materials, Drugs, Chemical substances, Biocides	Regulatory phase, Market phase, Design phase	Yes	Environment	Dynamic, quantitative environmental fate model based on colloidal chemistry. Estimates particle number concentrations in the aquatic environments resulting from processes such as materials inflow, homo- and heteroagglomeration/aggregation and sedimentation, which are considered driving forces behind the transport of NMs in waters and their potential elimination from them.	
OECD harmonised templates for physico-chemical properties (nci, nanomaterials) Owner: OECD				Guidance document, Resource	Web-tool		Chemical substances	Regulatory phase	Partly		The OECD Harmonised Templates (OHTs) are standard data formats for reporting information used for the risk assessment of chemicals, mainly studies done on chemicals to determine their properties or effects on human health and the environment, but also for storing data on use and exposure. They are aimed at developers of database systems, as they prescribe the formats by which information can be entered into and maintained in a database. By using these templates, governments and industry are	Hazard assessment

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The screenshot shows the SbD4Nano application interface. A 'Filters' dialog box is open, allowing users to refine search results. The dialog includes a 'Nanospecific' dropdown menu set to 'All', a 'Description contains' text input field, and a list of checkboxes for 'Exposure routes': 'Environmental' (unchecked), 'IngestionOnly' (checked), 'DermalOnly' (checked), and 'InhalationOnly' (unchecked). An 'Ok' button is located at the bottom right of the dialog. In the background, a table with columns for 'Label & owner', 'Exposure Routes', 'LifeCycle Stage', and 'Applicable Material' is visible, showing entries like 'CEM' and 'nanoinfo.org'.

Under the “Search for relevant publications” you will find the embedded ATENA document repository as described in Section 4.

The screenshot displays the 'SbD4Nano Datasets' page. The top navigation bar includes 'SbD4Nano', 'Cases', 'Accounts', 'SbD resources', 'Guidelines', 'Success stories', and user information for 'Ralph [SbD4Nano]'. A search bar is present with the text 'Search datasets...'. Below the search bar, it indicates '417 datasets found' and an 'Order by: Last Modified' dropdown menu. The main content area lists several dataset entries with titles and brief descriptions, each accompanied by a 'link' button. The entries include: 'Experimental methods used in determining chronic toxicity: a critical review', 'Predictability of chronic toxicity from acute toxicity of chemicals in fish a...', and 'Results of a two-year chronic toxicity and oncogenicity study of 2, 3, 7, 8-t...'. On the left side, there are filters for 'Groups' (nanoparticles: 160, properties: 100, safety: 157) and 'Keys' (years from 2001 to 2011 with counts).

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7.4 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the progress in making third-party resources available in the SbD4Nano knowledge platform. There is a wealth of published resources, but few of them are easy to reuse. Deliverable D1.1 previously outlined this wealth but subsequently we are running into a practical problem, unspecific to this project, and something other EU NanoSafety Clusters project run into as well: there is theoretical access, and that is practical access. In fact, this problem is much wider and one of the key aspects of the FAIR guiding principle.

We here report continued effort to solve a hard question: giving a set of chemical and biological properties of interest (wanted product properties, unwanted adverse outcomes), which resources have data or knowledge to help us study them for a particular nanomaterial. Data and knowledge is existing but scattered. If we are lucky, it has ontological annotations, helping the integration. But navigating this space of resources is currently still mostly manual work. We here show that using modern approaches, open standards, particularly community ontologies and knowledge graph theory, we can start supporting safe-by-design research.

Specifically, a knowledge graph framework has been developed that allows us to find information needed by our cloud platform. This Deliverable D1.2 and the task behind it, Task T1.2 shared this work with WP2: here we focused more on data, while WP2 focuses on the biological cause-effect relationships, sharing the same knowledge graph representation. Second, this deliverable reports on two added information sources to the e-infrastructure, the information resources extracted from the SbD landscape were made available to the user and the tool running at atena.arv.cat was embedded in the e-infrastructure.

8. Final remarks & Plan for the future

This deliverable has introduced various components of the SbD4Nano web based repository being developed in support of the user-oriented platform developed in WP5. It describes the efforts undertaken in Task T1.2, starting with a description of the Semantic Bioactivity Landscape (Section 2), which contains an RDF version of the overview of the available resources. When new resources come in (on top of the long list described in Deliverable D1.1), the semantic platform ensures we get alerted of new biological and chemical insights. In this way, the Safe-by-Design platform developed by the project can be sustained. It continues with an explanation of Atena, a website which acts as a document repository service (Section 4), an extensive description of the exposure triples in TNO's DIAMONDS FAIR Data Point (Section 5), and the NanoSafety Data Interface described in Section 6 that provides access to the aggregated search index of the (sub)set of eNanoMapper database instances. Section 7 discusses how the information described in the previous sections is integrated into the WP5 e-infrastructure.

As the SbD4Nano project continues, we will keep developing the public repository of available databases, nano-informatics tools, and models for hazard prediction, occupational, consumer and environmental risks estimation tools, decision making tools for risk governance, and SbD strategies. We therefore

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released the first aspects of it as open data, which will enable collaboration with other EU NanoSafety Cluster projects. In the coming period further effort will go into the aggregators that pull in (meta)data into the landscape, aligning with, for example, the just established ELIXIR Toxicology Community (14) and the Risk Governance Council (15). We will further seek collaboration with the nanoinformatics projects to adopt semantic annotation of computational services and further promote with NanoCommons the use of Bioschemas annotation of datasets (see Section 2).

Internally, with these solid foundations in place, we can think of automated synchronization of resources. That is, where this deliverable shows how the synchronization can be done in a meaningful way (using detailed semantics), in the next period we can work out and optimize these processes, leading to Deliverable D1.4 in month 48 of the project.

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